

THE STRUCTURE OF PIRLS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT SYSTEM. THE ROLE IN THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY AND EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In this study, the historical concept, stages of application, development directions, goals and objectives of the "PIRLS" program for assessing the level of knowledge and mental potential of international students, as well as the analysis of important aspects that affect the educational system of countries, have been investigated actively used the statistical research method. The analysis of the scientific research of several local and foreign research scientists related to the topic of our research was also carried out. As a result of the analysis of the scientific research of the analyzed researchers, we can see that the international "PIRLS" program has an indirect effect on several countries' sectors, in particular, the education system, economic sectors and fields, industrial sectors and many other sectors. World Bank, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar and other databases were actively used in the research, using the data of the last 5-10 years.*

Keywords: *PIRLS, PISA, society, education, economy, primary education, 4th grade pupils.*

Introduction

The most important categories of modern education have been developed since ancient times. It can be said that the goals and tasks of the educational system, its content, form and methodology are the traditional categories used for the analysis of educational strategies.

In particular, countries are actively using PIRLS, PISA, TIMSS and a number of other international student knowledge assessment programs in order to improve the current modern education system and analyze the economic growth trend. The results of PIRLS research, which is used in developed and developing countries, are widely discussed by economic and pedagogical researchers. The main goal of our research is to analyze the essence of the PIRLS evaluation program, the principles related to the educational system and the economy.

The Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) is an international student assessment program that assesses the reading literacy of fourth grade students. PIRLS was first used in 2001 by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) in the fields of the educational system. This framework provides participating countries with an overview of how their education systems should reform in terms of reading and comprehension literacy.

PIRLS assesses students' knowledge literacy by analyzing their comprehension and interpretation skills in a variety of texts. The assessment includes a variety of materials covering fiction, poetry and informational texts, and a number of other diverse fields. As a result, students' comprehension skills, vocabulary and the ability to draw conclusions from the text are checked. In addition to assessing students' reading ability, the PIRLS also looks at a variety of factors that may influence reading achievement, such as students' attitudes toward reading, classroom practices, and the socioeconomic environment in their homes.

The program is evaluated every five years, allowing for an overall analysis of trends in reading literacy achievement across countries. PIRLS results are used to inform educational policies and practices aimed at improving reading and developing literacy skills among young learners.

Overall, PIRLS plays an important role in advancing our understanding of reading literacy globally and in supporting efforts to improve educational outcomes for students around the world.

Literature review

Many domestic and foreign research scientists related to this topic, in particular, scientists such as O.Michael, O.Martin, D.Caro and M.Joncas have conducted their scientific research. Also, local researchers such as T.Umarov, U.Dolimovich, Z.Ismoilova and G.Tursunova gave their valuable opinions within the framework of their scientific research.

As a result of the studies reviewed, it is worth noting that PIRLS has two broad objectives in assessing students' learning in and out of the classroom. That is, it is aimed at "acquiring artistic experience" and "receiving and using information". Each of these goals, in turn, integrates four overarching understanding processes, which are:

Summarizing attention and finding specific information.

Drawing direct conclusions from data.

Identifying elements of materials and information and critical thinking.

Analyzing and integrating ideas and information.

Also, in the opinion of research scientists, they emphasized that the same test questions are not given to all students. The test questions used in PIRLS studies are usually designed to evaluate the effectiveness of the country's education system, and the research questions are not intended to evaluate individual students. Therefore, it was considered that it should not be required to distribute the same sample set of questions to each student. They also said that the set of PIRLS test materials will be distributed randomly among the students who participated in the test. We can understand that the PIRLS research is conducted using a computer technology system, the main

reason for which is that computers and computer technologies have become a part of our daily lives.

Methodology

In the methodology of our research on the nature of the PIRLS international assessment system and its impact on the education system and the economy, we actively used several research methods, in particular, comparative and contrastive analysis, research methods. This type of research includes steps such as: defining the main research hypothesis, collecting statistical data, and analyzing the collected data.

In the initial part of our research, general brief information about the article was given. In the second part, the introduction of the article, in the third part, the literature analysis and research methodology were formed. Also, in the key parts of our research, a scientific analysis of the nature of the PIRLS international assessment program, its impact on the education system and the economy was carried out. And finally, as a result of the analysis, conclusions and suggestions are given, the list of used literature is given, and the research is completed.

Analysis

Between the leaders participating in the PIRLS system, which is an international assessment program, and the schools and teachers studying the educational environment in the educational area, also, parents or other relatives of students took part in questionnaires that included various methods in order to study the conditions of their children's education.

As a result of its 15 years of research, the IEA international community has conducted research on the academic activities of more than 64 countries, more than 11,850 educational institutions, more than 338,500 students and more than 15,750 teachers. For more than 15 years, it can be noted that the level of reading and understanding of 4th graders has improved significantly.

The main research method of the PIRLS system is mainly divided into 2 types. These are:
reading new and popular literature;
learning experience aimed at acquiring new information.

Participants in the study read 2 different types of literature: fiction and informational. In this type of research, 4 types of knowledge skills of the participants are evaluated. These are to identify the necessary information and communicating this information, to draw the necessary conclusions from only a part of the texts containing various information, to show interpretations of the actions of the main participants in the text and to realize their thoughts with examples from the necessary parts of the text.

The PIRLS research system evaluates the learning of its students in the classroom and outside of school in two parts:

In order to evaluate the literary skills of students;
For the purpose of data acquisition and use.

According to research strategies, students' reading abilities are assessed in four groups while reading literary and informational texts:

Identifying the specific information provided;
Improving conclusions;
Data analysis;

Analysis and assessment of the nature of information, language features and text structure.

The following system is used for high-quality and reliable assessment of completed assignments of PIRLS international student knowledge assessment system:

By choosing an answer, 1 point is awarded for each correct answer.

1 point is given for correct answers regarding the correct identification of the sequence of the topic.

Tasks that must be answered independently and freely are given scores from 1 to 3 points depending on their complexity.

In the PIRLS assessment system, levels of reading literacy are assessed as follows:

The maximum level (620 points and above) - students can master the text in its entirety and at the same time understand its separate parts in relation to each other.

High level (545 points) - students understand the necessary parts of the text, express their opinions based on the text, pay special attention to the form and content of the text.

Intermediate level (470 points) - students get various information from the given text, express their opinions based on the text using some features of the text form and language.

Low level (395 points) - students clearly extract information from the text that is clearly presented and easy to identify.

We can see the impact of the PIRLS international student learning assessment system on the country's economy in several factors.

Education quality and workforce development;

The PIRLS international student assessment system provides important information about the quality of education systems in different countries. By identifying reading literacy strengths and weaknesses, policymakers can make informed decisions to improve educational outcomes. A skilled workforce with quality and reliable education is critical to economic growth as it boosts productivity, innovation and competitiveness.

Development of human capital;

Participation in the PIRLS program leads to improved human capital development in the country. This will make an important contribution to economic development and training of qualified personnel capable of attracting foreign investments.

Global competitiveness;

Countries that perform well in the PIRLS assessment make a significant contribution to excellence in education and student success. This can increase their global competitiveness by demonstrating their ability to produce highly skilled individuals who are proficient in reading literacy. A strong education system can attract multinational corporations seeking an educated workforce, thereby stimulating economic growth.

Long-term economic impact;

In the long run, participation in programs like PIRLS can have a lasting impact on the country's economy. Improved educational outcomes further enhance citizens' literacy, critical thinking skills, and problem-solving skills. These factors are necessary for innovation, entrepreneurship and sustainable economic growth.

Participation in the PIRLS international assessment program can have a positive impact on the country's economy by improving the quality of education, developing human capital, increasing global competitiveness, making political decisions and stimulating long-term economic growth.

Conclusion

The PIRLS international evaluation system plays an important role in evaluating and improving the educational standards of the countries of the world. By assessing fourth grade students' reading comprehension skills, PIRLS provides valuable information that can be used to identify areas for improvement in educational systems. The structural framework of PIRLS ensures that assessments are conducted consistently across participating countries and enables meaningful comparisons. This information is useful not only for politicians and teachers, but also affects the country's economy. Qualified personnel is important for economic growth and ensuring competitiveness in the world market. Therefore, based on the core objectives of PIRLS, PISA, TALISS, and other international student learning research programs, investing in education is critical to ensuring a prosperous future for any nation.

REFERENCES

1. Mullis, I. V., & Martin, M. O. (2019). PIRLS 2021 Assessment Frameworks. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement. Herengracht 487, Amsterdam, 1017 BT, The Netherlands.
2. Martin, M. O., Mullis, I. V., & Hooper, M. (2017). Methods and Procedures in PIRLS 2016. International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement.
3. Caro, D. H., & Cortés, D. (2012). Measuring family socioeconomic status: An illustration using data from PIRLS 2006. IERI Monograph Series Issues and Methodologies in Large-Scale Assessments, 5, 9-33.
4. LaRoche, S., Joncas, M., & Foy, P. (2016). Sample design in PIRLS 2016. Methods and procedures in PIRLS, 1-34.
5. Toxirjon, U. (2024). Learning international reading literacy (PIRLS). Integration of Economy and Education in the 21st century, 2(2), 14-17.
6. Dolimovich, U. D. (2024, June). International assessment programs. In interdiscipline innovation and scientific research conference (vol. 2, no. 21, pp. 25-28).
7. Zilola, I., & Muxlisa, N. (2023). Importance of international evaluation programs. Scientific Impulse, 1(7), 1005-1007.
8. Ibragimovna, T. G. (2022, April). PIRLS International Assessment Program and its importance. In Conference Zone (pp. 43-45).
9. M.Erejepov "The importance of the international PIRLS program in improving the quality of education". International multidisciplinary conference "prospects and key tendencies of science in contemporary world". Science and innovation, 2023.
10. F.Xudayqulova "International PIRLS Assessment Program". "Republican scientific-practical conference on "Pedagogical technologies of creating a cultural environment in secondary schools: problems and solutions", may 15-16, 2023y.
11. Faxriddin o'g'li, F. M. (2024). PIRLS-(Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) - about the literacy assessment system of international students. Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке, 2(20), 773-778.
12. Liu, H., Bellens, K., Gielen, S., Van Damme, J., & Onghena, P. (2014). A country level longitudinal study on the effect of student age, class size and socio-economic status-based on PIRLS 2001, 2006 & 2011. Educational policy evaluation through international comparative assessments, 223-243.